

Motor Vehicle Accident Severity Prediction Via Machine Learning

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Abstract — This study utilizes supervised machine learning on the U.S. Accident Dataset (7.7M records, 2016–2023) in order to predict crash severity. The dataset provides detailed accident records from all over the United States, including weather, location, time, and infrastructure conditions. Feature groups were created to isolate temporal, environmental, and spatial factors, and were trained on four models, KNeighborsClassifier, DecisionTreeClassifier, RandomForestClassifier, and RandomForestRegressor. These results were then evaluated using overall accuracy or mean squared error to compare results. Three sampling conditions were tested: raw imbalance data, SMOTE-resampled data, and SMOTEENN-resampled data. The results show that the RandomForestClassifier trained on the unbalanced infrastructure-based feature set (X2) had the highest accuracy at 87.97%, exceeding the accuracies of all other sampling-based models. While most models had a decreased accuracy with resampling, the regression models improved, showing their tolerance to synthetic noise. This research reinforces the idea that ensemble models perform strongly in class-imbalanced, real-world settings and highlights the predictive impact of infrastructure-related data on accident severity and emergency planning.

Keywords — Accident severity prediction, Machine learning, Traffic crash modeling, Imbalanced classification, Spatial risk factors, Road infrastructure features, Supervised learning, Random Forest classifier, SMOTE and SMOTEENN, U.S. traffic data

I. INTRODUCTION

Traffic accidents are among the leading causes of death and injury worldwide, making accident severity prediction a key area of study for improving public safety. Kaggle user Sobhan Moosavi provided the U.S. Accident Dataset, which contains data from February 2016 to March 2023 [1][2]. The dataset has a 10.0 usability score on Kaggle, indicating its credibility, and it was sourced from multiple APIs that provide traffic incident data, including those from the US and state departments of transportation, law enforcement agencies, traffic cameras, and traffic sensors. The US Accidents dataset contains 1.5 million+ records with 46 features, including temporal data (e.g., Start Time, End Time), location (e.g., City, Latitude, Longitude), weather conditions, road infrastructure

indicators (e.g., Junction, Crossing), and traffic signals.

A major advantage of this dataset is its size, with a total of 7,728,394 unique instances, which provides a large and diverse pool of training examples. The scale of this dataset enables machine learning models to capture complex patterns and relationships that smaller datasets may not support, ultimately improving accuracy in real-world scenarios.

This research applies supervised machine learning algorithms to classify accident severity based on a variety of temporal, environmental, and geographic features. The objective is to determine which model(s) provide the highest predictive performance, analyze the relative importance of each feature, and evaluate the potential for these models to be used in real-time safety alerts, risk assessments, and resource planning for emergency response teams.

II. SURVEY OF THE CURRENT FIELD'S STANDINGS

According to recent statistics, approximately 6 million motor vehicle accidents happen annually in the United States, with around 40,000 of them resulting in fatalities and millions more injuries [3]. Motor vehicle accidents continue to be the leading cause of death, and extensive research efforts have been made in the past two decades in hopes of identifying prevalent factors that aid in the prediction of accident severity. However, since many of these accident datasets vary, for example, by geographic coverage, number of features, or class distribution, the model best fit for the job does as well. By analyzing previous research, this project aims to avoid common pitfalls and build on the success of other projects.

One of the earlier approaches for the classification of crash data used logistic regression because of its simplicity. However, logistic

regression models struggle to effectively capture non-linear relationships in larger and more complex datasets. As a result, researchers began utilizing more robust models like Decision Trees and Random Forests. For instance, in a 2019 study by Zhang et al., researchers used California accident data and achieved over 75% accuracy using Random Forest and Gradient Boosted Trees, supporting the idea that these models are superior to traditional ones in their ability to capture feature interactions and importance [4].

Recent research has used ensemble-based models to boost performance (advanced machine learning techniques that combine multiple models to improve accuracy). A study conducted in New South Wales, Australia, used Random Forest, XGBoost, AdaBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost to classify accident severity and reported LightGBM achieving the highest ROC–AUC score of 0.68, indicating moderate predictive accuracy. The dataset was balanced using SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique), which generates synthetic examples of the minority class to address class imbalance, and performance was assessed using precision, recall, F1-score, and AUC-ROC instead of accuracy [5].

While tree-based methods are accurate, other models like Support Vector Machines (SVM) have been used as well. For example, a 2016 study used SVM with a Gaussian kernel to predict the accident severity, but results were sensitive to class balance, causing accuracy to vary [6].

Additionally, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have also been used, especially with larger datasets like the U.S. Accident Dataset compiled by Moosavi. Despite the fact that DNNs can outperform simpler models under ideal conditions, they function as black-box models, trading performance for interpretability [7].

Ultimately, while numerous models can be applied to predict accident severity, their success depends on the quality of data, feature engineering, class distribution, and interpretability. This project builds upon that foundation through the application of multiple supervised models to a national-scale database with over 7 million entries. These models include K-Nearest Neighbors, Decision Trees, and Random Forest classifiers due to their

interpretability and adaptability to tabular data, particularly for handling imbalanced severity classes through sampling techniques that evaluate feature importance. Although ensemble and neural models are well-supported, this project emphasizes transparency and simplicity for analysis.

III. DOMAIN AND ATTRIBUTE ANALYSIS

The U.S. Accident Dataset has dozens of features that define roadway conditions, environmental factors, and temporal data, and to analyze how these features influence accident severity, three different groups were organized: X1 (time and weather-related), X2 (location and environmental), and X3 (a comprehensive combination of both). Each of these datasets was paired with the target variable of severity, which was modeled as a multiclass classification task.

The X1 feature group is based on time and weather variables. “Start Time Float32” and “End Time Float32” are timestamp features in Unix Time format that represent the start and end timings of the crash. These temporal variables allow the model to learn patterns that are associated with high traffic concentration, nighttime driving, or longer incident durations. “Visibility(mi)” measures how far the driver could see in front of them at the time of the accident. This variable helps represent harsher weather conditions that can directly impact reaction time and perception. “Wind_Speed(mph)” quantifies wind strength, which can be dangerous during high gusts or storms. “Precepitation(in)” indicates the amount of snowfall or rain present at the time of the incident, acting as a crucial predictor for slippery road conditions. “State number” is a numerical encoding of the state’s name, and it was included. Although it is not directly related to weather, it can capture trends of bad conditions that are consistently present in some states. “Wind direction number” encodes direction labels into numbers in order to capture the effect of wind’s alignment relative to the vehicle. “Weather Condition Number” numerically captures conditions like fog, rain, or snow, which strongly affect road safety. Finally, “Sunrise to Sunset Number” encodes whether the crash occurred day or night, which serves as a proxy for visibility, traffic congestion, and driver alertness.

The X2 feature set has 15 features that represent infrastructure on the road and geography. “Start Lat” and “Start Lng” represent coordinates of accidents and models can use this data to identify higher risk regions. “Zipcode” presents localized geographic data and can reflect local policy effects and socioeconomic differences that can influence accident severity. Additionally, twelve binary features describe the presence of certain types of infrastructure on the road. “Amenity” indicates the existence of public amenities, like rest stops or parks, which may attract vehicle and pedestrian activity [8]. “Bump” refers to speed bumps, which are upwardly curved parts of the road used to slow down drivers [9]. “Crossing” flags pedestrian crossings or crosswalks, which can have a higher risk for accidents [10]. “Give Way” or yield marks areas where drivers must wait for others; these areas can have a higher risk for crashes since they have confusing rules for prioritized traffic flow [11]. “Junction” represents an intersection where vehicles, and sometimes pedestrians, converge, which is much more dangerous and can heavily influence accident severity [12]. “No Exit” indicates the entrance to a non-through road, so vehicles cannot pass through to another street [13]. “Railway” refers to a railway crossing, which is the intersection where a road and a railway meet [14]. “Roundabout” designates the area where there is circular traffic that helps calm down congestion and tension [15]. “Station” flags areas with passenger facilities that are often transit hubs for rail or bus services. [16]. “Stop” declares that the area has a stop sign, which requires a full stop that can be ignored sometimes. “Traffic Calming” points to features in the roads that are aimed at slowing down vehicles, like speed bumps or chicanes [15]. Finally, “Traffic Signal” denotes the presence of traffic lights, which can regulate vehicle flow and crash likelihood based on compliance.

The X3 feature dataset combines all the aforementioned features into a unified group of 25 features, which allows the models to capture interactions between time, environment, geography, and infrastructure. For instance, effects from poor visibility may differ depending on whether a crash happened at a junction or during nighttime. Combining all these types of data enhances the

model’s understanding of the multiple factors that influence accident severity.

IV. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS

To get a comprehensive understanding of the U.S. Accidents dataset, an exploratory data analysis (EDA) was needed before the creation of the model could begin. This dataset contains over seven million entries that collectively capture conditions at the time of the accident. This includes environmental, geographical, and infrastructure related variables. The end goal of the EDA was to better understand the distributions, relationships, and imbalances of the features in the dataset; a complete grasp of this would help reduce the impact of uneven feature representation and redundant variables on the model’s performance.

The target variable severity ranges from 1 to 4, but upon examining its distribution, it is clear that the dataset is significantly imbalanced. A majority of the accidents are labeled with a severity of 2, while the most critical accidents (severity 4) make up only a small fragment of the dataset. Later on, SMOTE was used to ensure that the underrepresented classes were given enough weight during training.

Figure 1. Distribution of accident severity levels showing class imbalance.

Infrastructure-related features like Stop, Crossing, Give Way, Junction, and Traffic Signal were analyzed via Seaborn count plots. The binary values for these features helped capture the spatial risk factors that were part of road design. For example, the Bump feature showed much more

accidents when no bump was present. The number of instances when there was a bump was so tiny that in order to be visualized, the graph had to use a logarithmic scale, suggesting that traffic calming features like bumps are potentially effective in reducing crashes.

Figure 2. Crash counts with and without bumps (log scale).

On the other hand, Junction and Traffic Signal were frequently flagged; this supports the notion that they are correlated with crash likelihood because of high vehicle convergence zones.

Figure 3. Crash counts with and without Traffic Signals.

Environmental conditions also played a role; features like weather condition and wind direction were analyzed to see how conditions like rain, fog, and crosswinds correlated with accident severity and frequency. The Sunrise sunset feature, which details if it was day or night during the crash, revealed that many of the crashes occurred during daylight hours.

Figure 4. Crash frequency by time of day (day vs. night).

However, severe accidents were proportionally more frequent during the night, which suggests that the lower visibility conditions and driver fatigue may play a role into the severity of the accident.

Figure 5. Severe crash frequency by time of day (day vs. night).

To explore spatial trends within the dataset, the accidents with a severity of 4 were plotted geospatially via the Geopandas library. This plot revealed dense clusters of accidents in urbanized areas like the Northeast Corridor, Southern California, and major metropolitan areas in Texas and Florida. The shapefile from the Natural Earth dataset was used to generate a base map of the U.S. for geographical context. The severity 4 accidents illustrate concentration patterns that correlate with population density and complex infrastructure design.

Figure 6. Geospatial distribution of severity 4 crashes in the U.S.A.

In addition to raw coordinates, the regional variation's influence on crash outcomes was also investigated. The dataset was filtered for crashes with a high severity (level 3 or 4); then, they were grouped by state and plotted on a barplot. The results show that Virginia (VA) ranked the highest, with over 11,900 severe crashes, surpassing more populous states like Texas, Florida, and California. This suggests that Virginia may experience more severe accidents on average due to various interacting factors. The graph can be seen in Figure 7 on Appendix page 1.

Temporal information was also used by extracting data from the "Start Time Float32" and "End Time Float32" variables. Since both of these are Unix timestamps, subtracting these would give the crash duration, the time between the start and clearance of the accident. To avoid extremely big outliers, only 3 hours' worth of duration was observed. The resulting boxplot showed that the median duration of Severity 4 crashes was higher than any other level, and many of the crashes lasted over 100 minutes. High-severity crashes like these usually have serious injuries, multiple vehicles, heavy debris, and other hazards, which all take up a lot of time to be resolved. Unexpectedly, Severity 2 crashes also showed high durations, which may reflect upon resolution time being delayed due to traffic congestion in high-volume urbanized areas.

To completely assess the relationship between infrastructure presence and crash severity, the proportion of crashes that were severe (Severity 3 and 4) was calculated for each infrastructure variable's presence. The comprehensive barplot

shows that only one feature was associated with a significantly higher proportion of accident severity in its presence: Junction. It reached over 26%, but all other features showed a lower rate of severe accidents when present. For instance, features like Bump or Crossing were more likely to be less severe by a large margin. This may suggest that many traffic management features can inherently lower the risk related to accident severity. This data also reinforces the importance of Junction as it may be a key player in predicting accident severity. The graph can be seen in Figure 8 on Appendix page 1.

The extra risk tied to Junction's presence reflects the compounded complexity of multi-directional intersections, where errors may compound severity. The fact that other features are not as prevalent in creating higher severity crashes shows that the infrastructure variables should not be treated equally in models, as some can amplify severity while others can dampen it. This EDA's findings have aided in the selection of spatial, environmental, and categorical features for the final model and preprocessing strategies to deal with class imbalances in the dataset.

V. MODEL PERFORMANCE & RESULTS

To assess the effectiveness of various machine learning models, 4 models were trained and evaluated: KNeighborsClassifier (KNC), DecisionTreeClassifier (DTC), RandomForestClassifier (RFC), and RandomForestRegressor (RFR). These models were tested on 3 different feature sets: X1 (time and weather variables), X2 (location and environmental factors), and X3 (a combination of both). The model's accuracy was used as the performance indicator for classification models, while mean squared error was used for regression.

Initially, the models were all trained on the original imbalance dataset in order to establish a baseline performance. The best result was achieved by the RandomForestClassifier, which was trained on the X2 dataset; it had an accuracy of 87.97%, showing the model's strength at using environmental and location features despite the data skew. On the other hand, the RandomForestRegressor that was trained on the X3 dataset had the lowest accuracy of just 14.70%,

showing the limits of the regression model on unbalanced data.

A complete summary of model performance for non-resampled data can be found below.

Table 1. Model accuracy trained on imbalanced data.

Model	Feature Set	Accuracy (or MSE)
Kneighbors	X1	0.811844789
DecisionTree	X1	0.7930134227
RFC	X1	0.8282068515
RFG	X1	0.1939255787
Kneighbors	X2	0.8758499531
DecisionTree	X2	0.8718110142
RFC	X2	0.8797325665
RFG	X2	0.1586238025
Kneighbors	X3	0.8280962539
DecisionTree	X3	0.8443572898
RFC	X3	0.8650411657
RFG	X3	0.1469929572

To address the imbalance in the severity feature, SMOTE was applied to the training data. This method increased the representation of underrepresented severity classes (1, 3, and 4) but led to a lower overall accuracy. For example, the DecisionTreeClassifier that was trained on the SMOTE-resampled X1 data had an accuracy of 77.41%, which was lower than the baseline by 1.89 percentage points. Similarly, a reduction of 21.83 percentage points was observed in the KNeighborsClassifier's performance for the X1 dataset, decreasing from 81.18% to 59.34%. This is likely because of its sensitivity to the spatial distribution of synthetic neighbors that were introduced by SMOTE. It should be noted that SMOTE resampling was not utilized on the X3 dataset due to computational constraints.

Due to computational constraints, SMOTE was not applied to the X3 feature dataset, and the RandomForest models had to use constrained hyperparameters for processing limits: `n_estimators=30`, `max_depth=10`, `max_features='sqrt'`, `max_samples=0.4`, and

`n_jobs=-1`. These constraints helped the training be possible despite the largeness of the dataset. The original baseline models for X1 were lost, so the hyperparameter-limited versions were used as replacements. The results for the SMOTE sampled models can be found below.

Table 2. Model accuracy trained on SMOTE-resampled data.

Model	Feature Set	Accuracy (or MSE)
Kneighbors	X1	0.593461343
DecisionTree	X1	0.7740980448
RFC	X1	0.608762094
RFG	X1	0.5102488781
Kneighbors	X2	0.7978690822
DecisionTree	X2	0.8202331908
RFC	X2	0.341395614
RFG	X2	0.4166035749

Afterwards, SMOTEENN was implemented on the training dataset to further refine resampling; this process combines oversampling and instance filtering via Editing Nearest Neighbors. This technique helps to reduce noise by removing misclassified or ambiguous data after resampling. Despite this, the overall accuracy became worse. For example, the SMOTE-resampled X1 dataset had an accuracy of 59.34% accuracy with the KNeighborsClassifier, but had an accuracy of 52.94% with the SMOTEEN-resampled X1 dataset. But the SMOTEEN-resampled X1 data (66.16%) did better than the SMOTE X1 data (51.02%) on the RandomForestRegressor model by 15.14 percentage points. This indicates that regression models may work better with noise removal and synthetic data better than classifier models.

Similarly, the same hyperparameters were used for the RandomForest models trained on the SMOTEENN-resampled data, and only the X1 data was resampled due to computational limits. Interestingly, the accuracies were lower for all the models except the RandomForestRegressor model when compared to their SMOTE-resampled counterparts. The results for the models ran on SMOTEENN-resample data can be found below.

Table 3. Model accuracy trained on SMOTEEN-resampled data.

Model	Feature Set	Accuracy (or MSE)
Kneighbors	X1	0.5293870554
DecisionTree	X1	0.6963149734
RFC	X1	0.5093880338
RFG	X1	0.6616080752

VI. CONCLUSION

These outcomes outline a clear trend: resampling techniques like SMOTE and SMOTEENN can create class balance theoretically, but they do not consistently improve prediction accuracy. In fact, the best performing models were the classifier models that were trained on the original unbalanced dataset, specifically the ones trained on spatial and environmental features in the X2 dataset. This suggests that preserving the natural class distribution when using a robust tree-based model can be more effective than using synthetically balanced data. Overall, the results show that the RandomForestClassifier that was trained on the unbalanced X2 feature group was the best in terms of accuracy, and the tree-based models consistently did better than the KNC and regression models. Regression, despite being the weakest overall, showed the best resilience to oversample noise, which can be seen by the improved accuracy of RFG with the SMOTEEN data.

The findings of this paper can inform safety agencies and urban planners that robust tree-based models, when trained on naturally unbalanced spatial and infrastructure data, may offer more reliable accident severity predictions without using synthetic balancing. Future research could possibly further this idea by incorporating real-time traffic data, connected vehicle data, and precise roadway sensors for model evaluation under changing circumstances. An expanded analysis of this research could include contrasts between rural and urban areas and multi-modal transportation systems. Putting aside the accuracy aspect, future work could delve into interpretable AI methods and causal inference frameworks in order to explain

why certain features in the dataset amplify or mitigate accident severity. Such efforts would both improve predictive power and also provide insight into possible actions needed to further reduce accident severity.

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Figure 7. Count of severe crashes compared by state

Figure 8. Comparison of severe crash rates across infrastructure features.